

Polarographic Studies on the Influence of the Concentration and Nature of Different Supporting Electrolytes on the Kinetics of the Electrode Process of Mn(II)

SUDHINDRA SWARUP SHARMA AND MUKHTAR SINGH

Chemistry Department, Agra College, Agra

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The polarographic behaviour of Mn(II) has been studied in a variety of supporting electrolytes of varying concentrations (0.05 to 1 M) viz., NaCl, NaClO₄, NaNO₃, KCl, KClO₄, KNO₃, KNO₂, KBr, KI, KH₂PO₄, pot. acetate, pot. tartrate, pot. citrate, pot. benzoate, NH₄Cl, NH₄NO₃, NHCNS, Mg(NO₃)₂, Ca(NO₃)₂, Sr(NO₃)₂, and Ba(NO₃)₂. It has been found that the reduction of Mn(II) at d.m.e. is quasi-reversible and diffusion controlled in all supporting electrolytes. The kinetic parameters, viz., the transfer coefficient (α) and standard rate constant ($k_{s,h}$), of the quasi-reversible electrode process have been calculated by Gellings' method. The influence of the concentration and nature of supporting electrolytes on the kinetics of quasi-reversible electrode process of Mn(II) has been discussed in terms of the values of $k_{s,h}$ and ' α '.

A survey of literature¹⁻⁵ reveals that the polarographic studies on Mn(II) still remain incomprehensive in as much as that no attempt seems to have been made with regard to the influence of the concentration and nature of a variety of supporting electrolytes on the kinetics of the electrode process of Mn(II) at d.m.e. With this aim in view the present study has been undertaken.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were either of A.R., B.D.H. or E. Merck, G.R. grade. Solutions were prepared in conductivity water. The resultant concentration of Mn(II) was maintained at 1.0×10^{-3} M in each case.

The experiments were carried out in a similar manner as described elsewhere⁶. However, a different capillary being used the d.m.e. had the following characteristics :

$h_{corr} = 61.30$ cm ; $m = 2.075$ mg/sec. ; $t = 3.45$ sec.
(in 0.1 M KCl, open circuit) ; $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.005$
 $\text{mg}^{2/3}\text{sec}^{-1/6}$.

Results and Discussion

(i) Mn(II) gives a single well defined wave in the majority of supporting electrolytes used. However, in some supporting electrolytes viz., NaNO₃, KH₂PO₄, Mg(NO₃)₂, Ca(NO₃)₂, Sr(NO₃)₂ and Ba(NO₃)₂ the waves become drawn out at higher concentration of these supporting electrolytes. The limiting current is diffusion controlled in each case as evidenced by the linearity of i_d vs \sqrt{h} plots. The plots of $E_{d,se}$ vs $\log i_d - i$ are linear in all the cases.

(ii) On applying different criteria^{7,8} of reversibility and irreversibility of the electrode process it has been found that the reduction of Mn(II) is neither totally irreversible nor does it fulfil the requirements of reversibility. The slope values of log plots lie in the range 0.040 V-0.050 V. These slope values suggest the quasi-reversible nature of the electrode process of Mn(II).

Gellings' method⁹ has been used to evaluate $E'_{1/2}$ (the reversible half-wave potential) and the kinetic parameters (' α ' and $k_{s,h}$) of the quasi-reversible electrode process.

The calculated values of $k_{s,h}$ are of the same order of magnitude as suggested by Delahay¹⁰ for quasi-reversible electrode processes.

(iii) It has been observed that the value of $k_{s,h}$ records a decrease with the increasing concentration of the supporting electrolytes, viz., NaCl, NaNO₃, KNO₂, KBr, KH₂PO₄, pot. acetate, pot. benzoate. The values of $k_{s,h}$ (cm/sec) for these electrolytes, in the concentration range 0.05-1.0 M, lie between $10.90 \times 10^{-3} - 5.72 \times 10^{-3}$; $4.65 \times 10^{-3} - 4.0 \times 10^{-3}$; $6.36 \times 10^{-3} - 5.32 \times 10^{-3}$; $6.78 \times 10^{-3} - 5.32 \times 10^{-3}$; $5.66 \times 10^{-3} - 5.12 \times 10^{-3}$; $6.67 \times 10^{-3} - 4.12 \times 10^{-3}$ and $5.63 \times 10^{-3} - 4.98 \times 10^{-3}$ respectively, while the values of ' α ' lie between 0.4384-0.4246 ; 0.3500-0.3408 ; 0.4525-0.4396 ; 0.4036-0.3776 ; 0.4386-0.4270 ; 0.4745-0.4136 and 0.4612-0.4412. From this it follows that the rate of the electrode reaction is retarded at increased concentrations of these supporting electrolytes. This suggests that with the increase in the concentration of the supporting electrolyte, the quasi-reversible electrode reaction is gradually pushed towards irreversibility. The decrease in the value of ' α ' with increasing concen-

trations of the supporting electrolytes lends further support to this conclusion¹¹.

However, the value of $k_{s,h}$ increases with increasing concentration of the following supporting electrolytes :

NaClO₄, KClO₄, KNO₃, KI, NH₄CNS, NH₄Cl, NH₄NO₃, pot. tartrate, pot. citrate, Mg(NO₃)₂, Ca(NO₃)₂, Sr(NO₃)₂ and Ba(NO₃)₂.

The values of $k_{s,h}$ (cm/sec) for these electrolytes, in the concentration range 0.05–1.0M, lie between 7.94×10^{-3} – 9.62×10^{-3} ; 6.18×10^{-3} – 6.85×10^{-3} ; 4.32×10^{-3} – 6.21×10^{-3} ; 5.72×10^{-3} – 6.43×10^{-3} ; 5.65×10^{-3} – 6.28×10^{-3} ; 4.67×10^{-3} – 1.68×10^{-3} ; 5.42×10^{-3} – 5.96×10^{-3} ; 4.81×10^{-3} – 5.86×10^{-3} ; 4.18×10^{-3} – 5.40×10^{-3} ; 5.10×10^{-3} – 5.42×10^{-3} ; 5.12×10^{-3} – 5.34×10^{-3} ; 5.88×10^{-3} – 6.42×10^{-3} and 5.00×10^{-3} – 6.25×10^{-3} respectively, while the values of ' α ' lie between 0.4240–4490 ; 0.4210–0.4426 ; 0.4356–0.4835 ; 0.4360–0.4475 ; 0.3460–0.3680 ; 0.3950–0.4384 ; 0.3865–0.4256 ; 0.4165–0.4438 ; 0.4545–0.4786 ; 0.3512–0.3685 ; 0.3200–0.3570 ; 0.3350–0.3730 and 0.3758–0.4215. An increase in the value of $k_{s,h}$ implies that the electrode reaction of Mn(II) tends towards reversibility at increased concentrations of the above supporting electrolytes. The increase in the value of ' α ' with increasing concentration of these supporting electrolytes is in conformity with this conclusion.

Taking different sets of supporting electrolytes such that when cation was varied anion remained identical and vice-versa, the effect of anions and cations at a certain concentration (0.1M) on the value of $k_{s,h}$ has been attempted.

The order of $k_{s,h}$ value is as follows :

(i) For univalent cations : NH₄⁺ > K⁺ > Na⁺ (in nitrates)

(ii) for bivalent cations : Sr²⁺ > Ba²⁺ > Ca²⁺ > Mg²⁺

(iii) for anions (in pot. salts) : ClO₄⁻ > I⁻ > NO₂⁻ > CH₃COO⁻ > NO₃⁻ > tart.²⁻ > C₆H₅COO⁻ > H₂PO₄⁻ > citr.³⁻ > Cl⁻ > Br⁻.

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References

1. J. N. GAUR and D. S. JAIN, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1965, **28**, 123.
2. J. N. GAUR and N. K. GOSWAMI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 1030.
3. J. N. GAUR, P. S. VERMA and D. S. JAIN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 586.
4. J. KORYTA, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1962, **6**, 67.
5. J. E. B. Randles and K. W. SOMERTON, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1952, **48**, 951.
6. S. S. SHARMA and M. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 693.
7. L. MERTES, 'Polarographic Techniques', Interscience Publ., New York, 1965, p. 217.
8. R. GOTO and I. TACHI, *Proc. Intern. Polarogr. Congr.* Vol. I, 1951, p. 69.
9. P. J. GELLINGS, *Z. Elektrochim. Ber. Bunsenges. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 477, 481, 799 and 1963, **67**, 167.
10. P. DELAHAY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 1430.
11. S. K. JHA and S. N. SRIVASTAVA, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1975, **30b**, 859.